

Non-invasive dendrochronological analysis of the Lauenburg epitaph, Schleswig

Aoife Daly

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The Lauenburg epitaph, Schleswig

This research contributes to the research project, ‘After the Black Death: Painting and Polychrome Sculpture in Norway, 1350–1550’. The project is co-led by Noëlle Streeton and Tine Frøysaker, based in Conservation Studies, University of Oslo (UiO).

In January 2016, photographs for non-invasive dendrochronological analysis were taken of wood components of the Lauenburg epitaph, Schleswig (fig. 1). Measurements of the tree-rings from these photographs were made subsequently and the results of this is presented here.

Fig. 1. Lauenburg epitaph, Schleswig. View of the baldachin of the object (photo Aoife Daly).

The wood

The epitaph is a single panel with a curved baldachin attached at the top. The object appears initially to be made from two vertically placed oak boards, but on close inspection it was observed that one board is widened with a very narrow oak board along its length. The panel is set in a frame. The end-grain of the boards was not accessible for viewing.

In order to attain tree-ring measurements of the two main boards, photographs were taken of the backs of the boards, at the top and bottom edges where the tree-rings are visible in the longitudinal section (fig. 2). The tree-rings were clearly visible on both boards.

The macro-photographs were marked up in Adobe Photoshop (version 11.0.2), and measured using the application "Able Image Analyser". Here, a ruler in the photos is used to calibrate the picture, and the measurements are made to 1/100mm precision. For calculation of the t-value ("t-test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used, embedded in the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997).

Both the main backing boards are dated (fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Lauenburg epitaph, Schleswig. The image of the longitudinal section of board 1 showing the tree-rings (photo Aoife Daly).

Results

Board 1 contained 127 heartwood tree-rings. No sapwood was observed on the board. The tree-ring curve from board 1 could be dated. The tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1373 to 1499.

Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date of the oak tree that was used to make this board can be placed at **after** AD 1512.

Board 2 contained 156 tree-rings, also only heartwood is preserved. The tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1310 to 1465. The tree for this board was felled **after** AD 1478.

If we assume that the trees for the two boards were felled in the same year, then this felling took place after AD 1512 (fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Lauenburg epitaph, Schleswig. Bar diagram illustrating the dendrochronological dating of the boards from the Lauenburg epitaph. The bars show the chronological position of the tree-ring curves. The arrows at the right-hand side indicate the dates for the felling of the trees used for making the boards. As no sapwood is preserved, the dates are *termini post quem*. Colour shading indicates the possible interpretation of the results (illustration: Aoife Daly).

Filenames	-	-	board 1 Z151001a	board 2 Z151002b	average Z151M001	
-	start	dates	AD 1373	AD 1310	AD 1310	
-	dates	end	AD 1499	AD 1465	AD 1499	
0M040004	AD1156	AD1597	10.36	6.24	9.37	Baltic 1 64 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
HEADSx11	AD1304	AD1521	9.97	3.86	6.81	Stirling heads Baltic (Crone pers comm)
0eqmar1a	AD1270	AD1454	3.54	7.28	5.96	Maria retable Niguliste corpus plank 5 (Daly 2015 unpubl)
Z114&5 T1	AD1348	AD1542	5.74	5.89	7.62	Cranach-Vejle Luther Melancthon P1 & P3 (Daly 2014d)
Z1010019	AD1353	AD1490	6.64	4.69	6.67	Kvæfjord 1 altarpiece Norway corpus back plank 1 (Daly 2014b)
B0261M01	AD1380	AD1493	6.05	-	6.23	Køge forundersøgelser barrel B1 2 timbers (Daly 2013b)
Z080001a	AD1384	AD1516	5.45	3.40	6.03	"Money-lenders" in private ownership plank 1 (Daly 2011)
Z1120049	AD1380	AD1472	5.81	3.30	6.02	Veien altarpiece Oslo side plank 6 (Daly 2014a)
B019M002	AD1374	AD1574	4.58	5.98	5.85	Helsingør Kulturværft two barrels 5 timbers (Daly 2009)
stirlingdoorsM1	AD1270	AD1524	6.28	4.00	5.84	Stirling Castle doors 10 timbers (Crone pers comm)
H11EOM01	AD1260	AD1495	5.59	4.75	5.59	Bordesholmer Altar 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
Z103M001	AD1234	AD1495	4.86	3.82	5.31	Slagen altarpiece 13 timbers (Daly 2013a)
B0352M02	AD1386	AD1489	5.10	-	5.20	Roskilde Stændertorvet barrel 3 timbers (Daly 2015)
Z102M006 gr...	AD1262	AD1490	4.53	3.77	5.12	Kvæfjord 2 altarpiece Norway group 1 11 timbers (Daly 2014c)
00655M02	AD1368	AD1611	4.83	3.20	5.10	B&W Grund Skib 5. 3 trees (Daly 1997)

Table 1. Lauenburg epitaph, Schleswig. The table shows the correlation (t-value) between the tree ring curves from the planks and the average of the two and a range of tree ring datasets. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Oak provenance

The tree-ring curves from the two boards cross-match at their dated positions producing a correlation of $t = 3.96$. An average of the two is calculated (Z151M001) of 190 years length. The correlation (t-test) between the tree-ring curves from the two boards and the average of the two and a range of tree-ring data for oak is shown in table 1. The material is dating with a range of

chronologies from Northern Europe achieving highest correlation with tree-ring datasets from Southern Baltic oak. The trees for the boards grew in the Southern Baltic region.

As the dendrochronological analysis indicates that the oaks used had grown in the Southern Baltic region a sapwood estimate for Northern Poland (15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)) is used.

filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	extra end	Ave ring width (mm)	interpretation / felling
Z151001a	Lauenburg epitaph Schleswig board 1	127	AD 1373	AD 1499	T	G	0	N	H4	2.43	after AD 1512
Z151002b	Lauenburg epitaph Schleswig board 2	156	AD 1310	AD 1465	T	G	0	N	H4	1.68	after AD 1478
Z151M001	Lauenburg epitaph Schleswig 2 timbers	190	AD 1310	AD 1499						1.99	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
Aoife Daly, ph.d.			3rd March 2017								

Table 3. Lauenburg epitaph, Schleswig. List of objects analysed.

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